

ROLE OF MICRORNA 21 ON ORTHODONTIC TOOTH MOVEMENT AND PERIODONTAL LIGAMENT REMODELLING: A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND

Orthodontic Tooth Movement involves mechanical force that induces resorption of alveolar bone on the pressure side and deposition of bone on the tension side. The period of orthodontic treatment can be influenced by microRNA expression which are small noncoding RNAs, 22-25 nucleotides long, which regulate the function of gene at the post-transcriptional level. They play a crucial role in osteoblastogenesis and osteoclastogenesis. Research indicates that microRNA 21 facilitates the osteogenic differentiation of periodontal ligament stem cells by stretch and is upregulated in line with the mesenchymal stem cells differentiation potential.

METHODOLOGY

A comprehensive electronic search was conducted across multiple databases including MEDLINE (NCBI PubMed and PMC), CCRCT, Science Direct, Google Scholar, Web of Science, K Hub, and ResearchGate, supplemented by a manual search of peer-reviewed journals for relevant articles. The search employed combinations of titles, abstracts, MeSH, and keywords (Noncoding RNA) AND (MicroRNA 21)

AND (Orthodontic Tooth Movement) AND (periodontal ligament remodeling). Additionally, a Risk of Bias assessment was carried out for the included experimental animal studies.

RESULTS

Total 5 studies were included in this systematic review. Role Of MicroRNA 21 on periodontal ligament remodelling and orthodontic tooth movement was included for evaluation of studies. It was found that MicroRNA 21 expression was increased in the periodontal ligament when orthodontic force was applied over the tooth. It also revealed the multiple mechanisms by which MicroRNA 21 affects bone remodelling.

CONCLUSION

This study provides theoretical basis to promote the reconstruction of periodontal tissue during orthodontic tooth movement.

Keywords: Micro-RNA21, periodontal ligament remodelling, orthodontic tooth movement, nucleotides, stem cell differentiation

Introduction

Orthodontic tooth movement (OTM) refers to the pathological and physiological reactions of the periodontal housing and alveolar bone to an applied orthodontic force.^[1] The force causes injury to the periodontal tissue resulting from compression and tension in the periodontal ligament and blood vessels constriction. As the periodontal tissue adapts to the strain and subsequent inflammatory reaction, the tooth will move in intended direction.^[2]

According to Burstone in 1962 explained that the movement of tooth occurs in 3 phases, which are- first Initial Phase, second Lag Phase and third Post Lag Phase. During initial phase, tooth displacement causes compression of periodontal blood vessels which will further result in focal necrosis in periodontal ligament called Hyalinization. The surrounding areas to the hyalinization become hyperaemic as the necrosis sites release pro-inflammatory cytokines. These cytokines attract osteoclasts to this area. Because of the pressure and strain placed on the teeth, a complex series of biological processes are triggered, enabling bone remodelling. To enable teeth movement, a variety of substances, including cytokines, proteins, neurotransmitters, prostaglandins, and transcription factors affect the production and resorption of bone. During bone remodelling, osteoclast precursors like monocytes interact with cytokines and RANKL. It induces differentiation of monocytes to form osteoclasts. Other cytokines like Tumour Necrosis Factor- α (TNF α), Interleukin-1 and 6 (IL-1 and IL-6) and Hormones are responsible for survival, expression and function of osteoclasts.^[3-5]

MicroRNAs are post-transcription gene regulators which can promote degradation of messenger RNA and/or inhibit the translation of messenger RNA molecules.^[6,7] Till Date, microRNAs have been extracted from

a variety of bodily fluids.^[8,9] Circulatory or Extracellular MicroRNAs are stable molecules which can undergo various harsh physiological conditions without being physically altered to much extent. Since microRNAs are involved in inflammatory reaction regulation during bone remodelling, some microRNAs- microRNA-21, microRNA-34, microRNA -146a, microRNA-150 and microRNA-200 have been identified as responsible for regulating the balance of Osteoprotegerin (OPG) and osteoclastogenesis.^[10-12]

MicroRNAs have been extensively studied in oncology, and pertinent data has emerged on their possible application as molecular markers for various cancer types.^[13] Certain miRNAs are utilized in dentistry as diagnostic and prognostic markers for various conditions, such as periodontal disease, oral squamous carcinoma, craniofacial abnormalities, including cleft lip and palate and homeostasis.^[14-16] Additionally, miRNAs have been observed in other oral conditions as periodontitis and pulpitis.^[17-19]

Since the first miRNA was identified about two decades ago, the biology of miRNAs has been studied in great detail. The results of this review suggest that they have a wider range of applications, encompassing both dentistry and oncology. Studies into miRNAs' functions in development and disease, especially cancer, have made them valuable tools and targets for novel treatment approaches.^[20-29] Additionally, they might be essential instruments for implementing innovative or more effective orthodontic care. Furthermore, within the past ten years, the study of miRNAs has grown significantly in significance within the orthodontics area.^[30] Both fixed and mobile orthodontics have advanced their methods recently, making it possible to accomplish more goals than in the past. Specifically, their apparent importance during specific tooth motions or their involvement in the regulation of biological mechanisms can offer future orthodontists a vital tool for a fresh perspective on the methods used in this area of dentistry.

Prior microarray research has shown that 53 distinct microRNAs, including microRNA 21, that has been shown to control osteogenesis of stretch-induced stem cells of the periodontal ligament (PDLSC) in vitro, are differently expressed in response to human PDLSC stretching. Additionally, microR-21 can support osteogenesis in mesenchymal stem cells of bone marrow and osteoclast development in vitro triggered by RANKL. However, it is still unclear how microRNA-21 regulates alveolar bone remodelling in vivo, especially in response to orthodontic stress.^[31-33] One of the microRNAs that is linked to hypoxia-regulated transcripts and has the ability to influence the expression of several genes is microRNA-21. It stimulates mesenchymal cell's capacity for osseodifferentiation, which may be related to the signalling pathway of extracellular signal-regulated kinase (ERK)-mitogen-activated protein kinase.^[34, 35]

MATERIAL AND METHOD

The current systematic review is reported using a protocol that was created in accordance with the PRISMA declaration.

ELIGIBILITY CRITERIA

Study criteria was designed following the PICO (Participant , Intervention, Control and Outcome) format.

PARTICIPANTS/POPULATION(P) - Mice under orthodontic treatment

INTERVENTION(S), EXPOSURE(S) - Orthodontic tooth movement

COMPARATOR(S)/CONTROL(C) - no treatment and split mouth study

PRIMARY OUTCOME: microRNA 21

SECONDARY OUTCOME(S): periodontal ligament remodelling

❖ **STUDIES TO BE INCLUDED:**

- In vivo studies
- Healthy laboratory animals
- Orthodontic tooth movement
- Periodontal tissue remodelling
- MicroRNA 21 effect

❖ **STUDIES TO BE EXCLUDED:**

- Only In-vitro studies
- Articles focused on intervention other than Orthodontic Tooth Movement
- Studies with altered systemic conditions
- Articles with incomplete study characteristics (observation period, control)
- Review article
- Languages other than English

INFORMATION SOURCES AND SEARCH STRATEGY

The literature search was done after the eligibility criteria were established. For the search strategy based on the aforementioned PI(E)COS query, free keywords and concepts from the Medical Subject Headings (MESH) regulated vocabulary were used. PRISMA formed the basis for the selection criterion. Articles related to MicroRNA 21 and OTM and periodontal ligament remodelling were collected from different databases. Two separate reviewers searched the studies that would be included in this systematic review; if there was a disagreement, a third examiner stepped in to settle the disagreement. The aforementioned databases were searched using the combinations of title, abstract, MeSH (Medical Subject Heading Terms) and keywords. (MicroRNA 21) AND (Orthodontic Tooth Movement) AND (Periodontal ligament remodelling) AND (Bone remodelling) AND (Rats OR Mice). Parallel or split mouth animal studies in mice or rats which have evaluated the role of the MicroRNA-21 on OTM and the effect on periodontal ligament remodelling in terms of clinical, histological or immunohistochemical profiles were rendered 'eligible' for present systematic review. Narrative case reports, literature reviews, in vitro studies, case series, interviews, commentaries were rendered 'non-eligible' for present systematic review. A comprehensive search was undertaken from the year of origin of the earliest study to identify and collect evidence from studies which have evaluated the role of MicroRNA 21 in periodontal ligament remodelling and OTM in order to answer the PI(E)COS question. Quality assessment of eligible studies was done using SYRCLE's RoB Tool.

ANNEXURES

TABLE 1: STUDY CHARACTERISTICS

Sr. No.	Study Id		Journal Name	Study Design	Approval Of Protocol
	Author	Year			
1	N. Chen et al	2016	Journal of Dental Research	Randomized controlled split mouth study	Fourth military medical university, West Changle, China
2	Hong Hong et al	2016	International journal of clinical and experimental pathology	Randomized controlled split mouth study	Sun Yat-Sen University, Guangzhou, China
3	Xueqin Zhang et al	2018	Experimental and Therapeutic Medicine	Randomized controlled split mouth study and in vitro study	Sun Yat-Sen University, Guangzhou, China
4	Lii Wu et al	2019	Oral Disease	Randomised controlled trial	School of Stomatology, Capital Medical University, Beijing, China
5	Y Zhang et al	2020	Molecular Medicine Reports	Randomised controlled trial	China medical university, Liaoning, China

TABLE 2: PARTICIPANT CHARACTERISTICS

Sr. No.	Study ID		Sample Characteristics					
	Author	Year	Species	Strain	Sex	Age	Weight	Sample size
1	N. Chen et al	2016	Mice	Wild type C57BL & MicroRNA 21 deficient	Male	-	-	48
2	Hong Hong et al	2016	Rats	Sparague-Dawley	Male	-	-	30
3	Xueqin Zhang et al	2018	Rats	Sparague-Dawley	Male	6-8 weeks	210± 15 g	30

4	Lii Wu et al	2019	Mice	Wild type C57BL & MicroRNA 21 deficient	Male	8 weeks	200-250 g	12
5	Y Zhang et al	2020	Rats	Sparague-Dawley	Male	8 weeks	286-320g	36

TABLE 3: METHODOLOGICAL/ INTERVENTION CHARACTERISTICS

Sr. No.	Study ID		Intervention characteristics				
	Author	Year	Teeth	Type of appliance	Magnitude of force	Observation time	Control
1	N. Chen et al	2016	Maxillary incisor to 1 st molar	NiTi Closed Coil Spring	30 g	0, 3, 5, 7 days	Split mouth
2	Hong Hong et al	2016	Maxillary incisor to 1 st molar	NiTi Closed Coil Spring	50 g	0, 1, 3, 7, 14, 21 days	Split mouth
3	Xueqin Zhang et al	2018	Maxillary incisor to 1 st molar	NiTi Closed Coil Spring	50 g	1, 3, 5, 7, 14, 21 days	Split mouth
4	Lii Wu et al	2019	Maxillary incisor to 1 st molar	NiTi Closed Coil Spring	30-35 g	14 days	Split mouth
5	Y Zhang et al	2020	Maxillary incisor to 1 st molar	Tension spring	25 g	7 days	Control group

TABLE 4: SUMMARY OF PRIMARY AND ADDITIONAL OUTCOMES

Sr No	Study ID		Outcome Measures							
	Author	Year	Type of screening	Place of screening	Protein 1	Protein 2	Protein 3	Protein 4	Protein 5	Protein 6
1	N. Chen et al	2016	qRT-PCR microcomputed tomography	Alveolar bone and periodontal ligament	MicroRNA 21	PDCD 4	Alp	RUNX2	RANKL	OPG
2	Hong Hong et al	2016	In situ hybridization & immunohistochemical staining	Alveolar bone and periodontal ligament	MicroRNA 21	PLAP-1	-	-	-	-
3	Xueqin Zhang et al	2018	qRT-PCR & immunohistochemical staining & Western Blotting	Alveolar bone and periodontal ligament	MicroRNA 21	HIF-1 α				
4	Lii Wu et al	2019	ELISA, qRT-PCR, immunohistochemical staining, microcomputed tomography	Alveolar bone and periodontal ligament	MicroRNA 21	OPG	RANKL	-	-	-
5	Y Zhang et al	2020	TRAP Staining, qRT-PCR, immunohistochemical staining, microcomputed tomography	Alveolar bone and periodontal ligament	MicroRNA 21	RANKL	PDCD 4	-	-	-

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

STUDY SELECTION

136 items were found after a thorough search across several databases. Two impartial reviewers found pertinent articles, and 83 duplicates were eliminated. After the analysing of titles and abstracts, 53 papers were chosen for full text examination. Complete texts were sought out and acquired for publications for which there were only abstracts available. The relevant authors were contacted for works published in languages other than English, and a translated version of the manuscript was requested. There were seven in vivo study publications found. 46 items were eliminated once the inclusion criteria were applied. There were five articles in total that met the

inclusion requirements. As a result, five publications met the requirements to be part of the current systematic review. Data was taken from these articles and examined closely to determine the function of MicroRNA 21 in Orthodontic Tooth Movement and periodontal ligament remodelling

CHARACTERISTICS OF INCLUDED STUDIES

Every study that was included involved in-vivo tests carried out on rats or mice. Every one of the five research was carried out in compliance with the ethical rules that govern studies involving animals. The ethical committee's approval of the protocol was requested by each author of the included research. Amongst the included studies, 4 were split mouth designs. All 5 studies were conducted in China. Sample size of the included studies was 12-48 mice/rats on average. All were male rats. Species included are wild type, Sprague-Dawley type and MicroRNA 21 deficient Rats procured from animal laboratory. Each trial's participants were chosen in accordance with its unique inclusion criteria.

SUMMARY OF METHODOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF STUDIES ON EFFECT OF MICRORNA 21 ON OTM AND PDL REMODELLING

Role of MicroRNA 21 was evaluated in OTM and its effect on various mediators in periodontal ligament remodelling were assessed in the included studies. All the studies included were performed in rats or mice with or without microRNA 21 deficiency. 4 studies were split mouth studies and in one study, a separate control group was taken. In 4 studies, NiTi Closed coil spring was used for active OTM. In one study, tension spring was used along with PAOO intervention. Qualitative assessment of periodontal ligament was done in all the studies.

SUMMARY OF PRIMARY AND ADDITIONAL OUTCOMES

Parameters recorded in 5 studies included expression of MicroRNA 21 on the side of pressure and tension of OTM, its effect on other bone remodelling factors, OTM in the presence and in the absence of MicroRNA 21.

SUMMARY OF THE PARAMETERS EVALUATED AND METHOD OF EVALUATION

The studies evaluated the expression of MicroRNA 21 on pressure and tension surface of OTM, its effect on other bone remodelling factors, OTM in presence and absence of MicroRNA 21 using Immunohistochemical assay or in-situ hybridization to detect expression of microRNA 21.

Studies (year)	Randomisation	Baseline characteristic similarity	Allocation concealment	Random housing	Blinding of researchers	Random outcome assessment	Blinding outcome assessors	Complete outcome data	Selective outcome reporting	Other factors resulting in high risk of bias
Hong Hong et al 2016	?	+	+	+	+	?	+	-	?	+
Bingdong Sui et al 2016	-	+	+	+	-	?	+	+	-	?
Xueqin Zhang et al 2019	+	?	+	?	+	+	?	+	+	?
Y Zhang et al 2020	+	+	+	+	+	+	?	+	-	+
Lili Wu et al 2020	-	+	+	?	+	?	+	+	?	+

RISK OF BIAS WITHIN THE INCLUDED STUDIES**DISCUSSION**

Wei et al. (2014) suggest that microRNAs may exhibit mechanosensitivity and function as essential posttranscriptional regulators during the process of bone remodelling.^[41] Previous research revealed that the microRNA expression profile of stretched PDLSCs (periodontal ligament stem cells) in culture differed from that of normal PDLSCs, with microRNA 21 being associated with osteogenesis induced by mechanical force. N Chen et al. (2016), in their study, also discovered that In response to orthodontic force, microRNA 21 is active and plays a crucial role in OTM in vivo. Only at the tensile surface of orthodontic tooth movement, where orthodontic strain stimulated osteoblastogenesis, was microRNA 21 function in osteogenesis detectable. In this work, it was established that there is differential alveolar bone remodelling in the two OTM sides and that microRNA 21 deficiency on both sides inhibits the rates of bone resorption. Moreover, microRNA 21 deficient animals displayed suppressed alveolar osteoclastogenesis in physiologic settings, which underlies elevated maxillary bone mass. They also found that microRNA 21 did not suppress OPG expression or increase RANKL, suggesting that microRNA 21 directly regulates osteoclastogenesis in osteoclasts.

Yoshimatsu et al (2006) suggested that OTM is regulated by T cells through proinflammatory cytokines. Okamoto et al (2015) found that OTM is influenced by periodontal conditions. In the study by N Chen et al (2016), periodontal microRNA 21 reacted to the initial inflammation and helped to cause Lipopolysaccharide-induced bone remodelling. These results showed that, in the context of the periodontal inflammatory environment, orthodontic tooth movement is post-transcriptionally regulated by microRNAs.

Studies by Kou I et al (2010), Kajikawa et al (2014) and Zhang P T et al (2011) suggested that PLAP-1 inhibited collagen formation and suppressed mineralization in periodontal ligament. PLAP-1 overexpression

acts as negative feedback in mesenchymal stem cells osteogenic differentiation. Ng TK et al found that PLAP-1 is one of the functional target of MicroRNA 21. Hong Hong et al (2016) detected the expression pattern of MicroRNA 21 and its functional target PLAP-1 during orthodontic tooth movement. They also found that upregulation of MicroRNA 21 promotes osteoclastogenesis. In-vitro studies by Takanari et al suggested that MicroRNA 21 was highly expressed in 4 hours and downregulated after 14 days after induction of mineralization of mesenchymal cells. Combined results of Hong Hong and Takanari suggest that MicroRNA 21 is more expressed in early stage of mineralization and decreased in late period, hence it can be the initiator of osteoclast differentiation.

Orthodontic force causes local hypoxia in periodontal ligament. Nallamshetty et al introduced a group of MicroRNAs called 'HypoxiamiRs' which are MicroRNAs in regulating gene expression in response to hypoxia. MicroRNA 21 was one of the hypoxiamiRs involved in cellular adaptation to low oxygen tension.

Xueqin Zhang et al found that MicroRNA 21 mimics increased HIF 1 α expression and MicroRNA 21 inhibition suppressed HIF 1 α expression. This suggests that MicroRNA 21 affects HIF 1 α in periodontal ligament under hypoxia.

Lili Wu et al (2019) found that MicroRNA 21 deficiency suppressed the orthodontic tooth movement and osteoclast number. Their study showed decrease in RANKL expression in MicroRNA 21 deficient mice, resulting in severe imbalance in RANKL/OPG ratio. They also found that the inhibition of RANKL/OPG ratio was enhanced by activated T cells and osteoclast differentiation in MicroRNA 21 deficient mice. Therefore, they concluded that MicroRNA 21 promoted OTM through RANKL and OPG.

Loh et al (2009) reported that transcription factor activator protein (AP 1) activity is altered by PDCD4 expression which triggers the transcription of MicroRNA 21. Zhang Y et al (2020) discovered that the agomiR-21 group had significantly lower PDCD4 expression levels than the PAOO group, whereas the PDCD4 expression levels was significantly higher in antagomir-21 group than the PAOO group. The findings indicated that during PAOO-mediated TM, MicroRNA 21 adversely controlled PDCD4 expression. Additionally, the outcomes showed an increase in C-Fos expression levels. Overexpression of MicroRNA 21 negatively regulated the target gene PDCD4's expression levels, which in turn led to increased levels of C-Fos, enhanced osteoclast generation mediated by RANKL, remodelling of the alveolar bone, local alveolar osteoporosis and development of temporary osteopenia, and increased movement of orthodontic teeth when treated with agomiR-21 and decreased when treated with antagonistIR-21.

CONCLUSION

Although the wide variety of mediators have been studied in OTM, only little is known about their exact mechanism and the affecting factors. In this study, we compiled and analysed the role of MicroRNA 21 on OTM and on various factors previously known for bone remodelling during OTM. We can conclude that microRNA 21 is an important mechanosensitive factor during orthodontic tooth movement and is involved in initiation of osteoclastogenesis during periodontal ligament remodelling. It has various ways of expression to

control the alveolar bone remodelling. It is upregulated in hypoxic condition and it maintains the RANKL/OPG balance during OTM. The findings in this study provide theoretical basis to promote periodontal reconstruction during OTM.

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